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Thesis · September 2021

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27320.67847/1

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AWARENESS LEVEL OF SELECTED MICRO AND SMALL ENTERPRISES IN CAVITE TOWARDS GREEN MARKETING: A BASIS FOR POLICY INTERVENTION

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ABSTRACT

Green marketing refers to a variety of ideas and tactics for selling goods and services in an ecologically sustainable manner. More specifically, it entails a variety of activities such as product development, process adjustment in operations, and corporate strategies that are aligned with environmental conservation and preservation methods. Hence, the researchers attempted to determine the level of awareness of selected micro and small enterprises in Cavite towards green marketing concepts and strategies to augment a systematic basis in crafting programs, strategies and policies which promotes environment-responsible production in the province. The researchers used descriptive and inferential research designs in the conduct of the study. The proponents found out that the enterprises were start-up to young enterprises, mostly on sole proprietorship organization type and have small number of staffs. The participants were moderately aware in relation to concept concerning green marketing, somehow aware as to green marketing strategies and finally, the micro and small enterprises under study were not engaged in green marketing strategies. Considerably, there are no significant relationships between the participants' profile with their awareness level towards concepts and strategies as well as their engagement level as regard to green marketing practices; and the challenges identified were: the engagement or participation in green marketing is costly, they have lack of knowledge and skill and they are not interested due to personal reasons.

Keywords: awareness, green marketing, marketing practices, micro and small enterprises strategies, policy intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Marketing as a unique and recognized discipline in business is dynamic and responsive. It evolves, modify and improve on various facets of creating value among products and services from enterprises to its final consumers. Marketing nowadays, is more varied, strategic and responsive compared on the previous decades hence, green marketing was conceived as a response for an environment-responsible production and was a growing concept at the onset of early 2000s (Moravcika, Kliestikova and Rypakova, 2017).

Green marketing pertains to the different concepts and strategies pertaining to the marketing of goods and services in an environmentally friendly way. More so, it involves various activities including product innovation, modification of process in operations and business strategies that align with environment conservation and preservation practices (Laheri, Dangi, and Vohra, 2014). The current and modern society poses adjustments in creating pathways for more responsible business activities as related to environment protection and conservation. Hence, green marketing is a growing concept related to sustainable internal business operations and corporate social responsibilities.

Thus, the researchers attempted to conduct an inquiry on the level of awareness of selected micro and small enterprises in Cavite towards green marketing concepts and strategies to augment a systematic basis in crafting programs, strategies and policies which promotes environment-responsible production in the province.

OBJECTIVES

Generally, the researchers analyzed the awareness level of selected micro and small enterprises in Cavite towards green marketing concepts and strategies.

Specifically, the researchers attempted to:

1. determine the profile of micro and small enterprises in terms of:
 - a. length of operations;
 - b. type of business organization; and
 - c. number of staff;
2. determine the level of awareness of micro and small enterprises towards green marketing in terms of:
 - a. Key concepts; and
 - b. Strategies;
3. determine the significant relationship of micro and small enterprises' profile and their awareness level towards green marketing;
4. determine the perceived challenges or constraints that impedes entrepreneurs to engage or participate in green marketing; and
5. propose strategies to boost green marketing practices in entrepreneurship among micro and small enterprises

REVIEW OF RELATED STUDIES AND LITERATURE

A green promotion is also known as the communication that promotes the product. In addition to supporting the green advertising campaign, it should also include the features to boost social

responsibility in the corporate picture. The success of green innovation and green promotion is therefore a success factor that affects the output of companies. Finally, the success of businesses is calculated in terms of economic performance (financial returns, market share, and growth in sales) and operational performance (aspects related to improving process efficiency, such as product quality). The authors concluded that green innovation, product and process efficiency has a positive impact on the company's performance, while the process of green innovation is seldom addressed in the literature, it is very important to highlight the process of green innovation, as it is easy to mimic the final product compared to the process. In view of the rapid and accelerating growth of green goods worldwide, marketers need to seize this opportunity to recognize the best green marketing strategy in order to win the desires and wishes of consumers (Hasan and Ali, 2015). Green marketing pertains to the different concepts and strategies pertaining to the marketing of goods and services in an environmentally friendly way. More so, it involves various activities including product innovation, modification of process in operations and business strategies that align with environment conservation and preservation practices (Laheri, Dangi, and Vohra, 2014).

A study entitled Consumers' Preferences on the Use of Eco-Friendly Bags: A Green Marketing Perspective (Gano-an, 2018). The authors identified that there's a change in consumer behaviour with regards to living eco-friendly. The problem with minimizing the effect of plastic products on the surrounding keep on prevailing even there are numerous green marketing campaigns led by the environmentalists. This study provided an analysis of the emerging issues caused in hypermarkets and supermarkets by using plastic bags with the coordination of environmentalists and the government sector, this study aims to lessen the usage of plastic bags when shopping and promote environmental campaigns in order to established awareness among consumers. This paper sought to understand the view of local customers and address the differences in order to assess the consumers' preferences on the use of eco-friendly shopping bags. The researcher formulated a survey questionnaire that aligns with the research objectives so as to provide accurate results. The consumers' preferences and perceptions on the use of eco-friendly bags were the main variables of the study. The demographic data of respondents were the independent variable while consumer awareness, environmental benefit, price, and public acceptance were the dependent variables of the study. It assessed the level of awareness of the eco-bags movement. Based on the data provided, most of the respondents were female consumers, the majorities were young professional ages 20 to 29 years old, and most of them were already married. Moreover, consumer awareness resulted that consumers were highly aware of the campaigns being advertised by the environmentalist on used eco-friendly bags instead of using plastic bags. Environmental benefit reveals that consumers were highly acknowledged the environmental benefits of using eco-friendly bags as a substitute for plastic bags and also it shows that consumers are aware of how to protect the environment. Price, it perceived that consumers were highly willing to purchase eco-bags on its price range. Since the consumer can still use it once they go shopping again. In comparison, eco-friendly products are way too expensive than the conventional ones, but still willing to buy these products. Public acceptance reveals that local consumers highly accepted the green marketing campaigns by the environmentalists and government it is because consumers know the harmful effect of plastic on the environment. As to moderating variables, only gender shows a significant difference, it shows that most females showed interest in environmental marketing. While marital status and age, show no significant difference. It means these variables don't affect their awareness of environmental marketing. The study concludes that consumers are highly aware of the environmental campaigns led by the environmentalists and the government. The movement of using eco-friendly products brings interest to consumers.

The main problem of green marketing researches that have been conducted in South Africa is that it lacks an indication of the awareness level of green marketing and the managerial implications of it to the manufacturing sector in the country specifically in the province of KwaZulu-Natal (KZN). This study aims to investigate the level of awareness regarding green marketing in selected South African Manufacturing Small, Medium, and Micro Enterprises (SMMEs) and secondly, its managerial

implications in KwaZulu-Natal (KZN). The author conducted the study to show an exploratory study with regards to the awareness level of green marketing and its managerial implications associated with the South African manufacturing sector. The result of the research study reveals that the South African Environmental Act and Consumer Protection Act are also additional factors that influence their business operation as indicated by the SMMEs' owners/managers. The author of the study concludes that South African Manufacturing Small, Medium and Micro Enterprises (SMMEs) need to increase their awareness, knowledge, and understanding regarding the green marketing concept and its benefit to their sector for them not to pay expensive marketing consultants. Further, the study identified that the lack of skilled marketing personnel is the ultimate barrier that hinders companies to practice green marketing and the lack of having marketing specialists makes SMEs spend a huge amount of money to acquire marketing consultants. Due to the conclusions that the author has made, thus, the study recommends that the SME owners or managers are needed to undergo training programs with the help of government training centers and public institutions for them to be able to train their employees. The study also recommends conducting customer training with regards to green products so that the customers will become more aware of green marketing (Lekhanya, 2020).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers used descriptive-correlational research designs in the conduct of the study. Descriptive design was used to describe respondents' profile and their respective awareness levels toward green marketing. Considerably, inferential design through correlation (Spearman-Rho) was employed to facilitate the determination of significant relationship between respondents' profile and their awareness level. Moreover, non-parametric purposive sampling design was used across the province to identify respondents and digital survey methods will be employed through online forms and scheduled phone calls. One hundred fifty entrepreneurs were selected from each of micro and small enterprises categories, a total of 300 participants.

Participants of the Study

The authors have utilized the registered micro and small enterprises registered in the province of Cavite under the Department of Trade and Industry, CALABARZON Region IV-A. The study initially targeted 300 participants purposively; 150 from microenterprises and 150 from small enterprises, the study retrieved the following; 112 from microenterprises (representing the 74.67% of the targeted sample), 115 from small enterprises (representing the 76.67% of the targeted sample) and a total composite sample of 227 participants collectively (64.86% of the total targeted sample size).

Sources of Data

The study used both the primary and secondary data sources in collecting the data. The primary data are from the participants and also the results from the survey questionnaires which were distributed through Google forms, multimedia survey approaches and flexible retrieval approaches. The secondary source of data came from the internet such as research studies, journals, e-books, and any related sources that will support the study.

Data Analysis

The researchers used the following data matrix for liker-type scaling in the survey questionnaires.

Table 1: Likert-scale of Awareness Level

Quantitative Value	Qualitative Value	Description
5	Highly Aware	Expresses highest awareness towards the concepts, mechanisms, operations, formulation and execution.
4	Moderately Aware	Shows awareness but not fully towards the concepts, mechanisms, operations, formulation and execution.
3	Somehow Aware	Expresses awareness but has a major gap in fully identifying the rigor of concepts, mechanisms, operations, formulation and execution
2	Not Aware	Responding no awareness to the rigor of the concept but is knowledgeable towards the term used.
1	Extremely Not Aware	Total unawareness towards the whole concept and rigor.

Table 2: Likert-scale of Engagement Level

Quantitative Value	Qualitative Value	Description
5	Highly Engaged	Expresses highest and full participation and engagement towards green marketing concept and activities
4	Engaged	Shows engagement towards green marketing concept and activities but has minor reservations.
3	Somehow Engaged	Expresses engagement towards green marketing concept and activities but has major reservations.
2	Not Engaged	Responding with no engagement but has plans to participate given an opportunity.
1	Highly Not Engaged	expresses strong intention of not engaging and participating towards green marketing concepts and strategies

FINDINGS

The researchers have tabulated, organized and treated data from the instrument used in this study. Below are the findings of this baseline study.

Table 3. Length of Operation

Years	Frequency	Percentage
0 to 1 year	108	47.60
2 to 3 years	59	26.00
4 to 5 years	13	5.70
6 years and above	47	20.70
Total	227	100.00

Table 3 shows the length of operations of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It implies that most of the enterprises are operating one year and below and considerably 5.70 percent are operating from four to five years which has the least percentage. This showcases that enterprises were start-up enterprises in the province as far as micro and small enterprise are concerned.

Table 4. Type of Business Organization

Types	Frequency	Percentage
Sole Proprietorship	182	80.20
Partnership	36	15.90
Cooperative	9	4.00
Total	227	100.00

Table 4 presents the type of business operation of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It shows that most of the enterprises are sole proprietorships and noticeably 4.00 percent are cooperative which has the least percentage. These indicate that enterprises were the sole proprietorship enterprises category in the province.

Table 5. Number of Staff

Staffs	Frequency	Percentage
1 to 15 staffs	220	96.90
16 to 30 staffs	7	3.10
Total	227	100.00

Table 5 reveals the number of staff of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It depicts that most of the enterprises have 1 to 15 staffs. Significantly 3.10 percent are operating with 16 to 30 staffs which have the least percentage. This showcases that enterprises have small to medium staff composition.

Table 6: Awareness of the Concept of Green Marketing

Category	Mean Value	Descriptive Value
1. Are you aware of the concept of green marketing?	3.74	Moderately Aware
2. Are you aware that green marketing products are presumed to be environmentally safe?	3.92	Moderately Aware
3. Are you aware that green marketing raise awareness on important environmental or social issues?	3.96	Moderately Aware
4. Are you aware that green marketing undergoes product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising?	3.77	Moderately Aware

5. Are you aware that green marketing adhering to sustainability principles while achieving maximum profit potential?	3.57	Moderately Aware
6. Are you aware that green marketing helps in waste reduction?	3.96	Moderately Aware
7. Are you aware that green marketing brings a competitive advantage to your business?	3.54	Moderately Aware
8. Are you aware that green marketing creates a wider choice of marketing points that can promote and discuss with the customers, which go beyond traditional strategies such as having the lowest price, durability and style?	3.59	Moderately Aware
9. Are you aware that green marketing can be more expensive, but it can also be profitable due to the increasing demand?	3.88	Moderately Aware
10. Green marketing describes a business' efforts to advertise the environmental sustainability of their business practices?	3.83	Moderately Aware
Grand Mean: 3.78		Moderately Aware

Table 6 reveals the awareness of the concept of green marketing among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It pertains to the fact that most of the enterprises are moderately aware of green marketing and 3.57 is the least average of businesses that are moderately aware of green marketing. It shows that most of the businesses in the province are moderately aware of the concepts of green marketing. Generally, the participants are moderately aware as far the awareness towards green marketing is concerned. It implies that there is presence of awareness but not fully towards the concepts, mechanisms, operations, formulation and execution.

Table 7: Awareness of the Strategies of Green Marketing

Category	Mean Value	Descriptive Value
1. Are you aware of green product designing where products are designed in environment friendly way?	3.37	Somehow Aware
2. Are you aware of green positioning where core component of its corporate practices, an organization should specifically support its sustainable output and that of its goods and services?	3.06	Somehow Aware
3. Are you aware of green pricing where a business should illustrate how a green product or service will help to conserve key resources for customers and actively participate in sustainability?	2.97	Somehow Aware
4. Are you aware of green logistics where includes all activities forward and reverse flows between the point of production and the point of consumption of goods, information and services?	3.03	Somehow Aware
5. Are you aware of green waste disposal where unsustainable disposal practices can be hazardous to both the environment and human health?	3.13	Somehow Aware
Grand Mean: 3.11		Somehow Aware

Table 7 shows the awareness of the strategies of green marketing of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It pertains that most of the enterprises are somewhat aware of the green product designing and 3.37 is the average of businesses that are moderately aware of the green pricing. It shows that most of the micro and small enterprises under study responded somehow aware towards the strategies of green marketing which means that they have expressed awareness but have a major gap in fully identifying the rigor of mechanisms, operations, formulation and execution.

Table 8: Engagement level in Green Marketing and Strategies

Category	Mean Value	Descriptive Value
Engagement level in green marketing and strategies (Green design, green positioning etc.)?	2.30	Not Engaged

Table 8 shows the engagement level of micro and small enterprises in Cavite in green marketing and strategies. It implies that most of the enterprises are not engaged in green marketing strategies by having a mean value of 2.30 which means that the small and microenterprises understudy responded with no engagement or participation towards strategies but has plans to participate given an opportunity.

Table 9. Correlation of Length of Operations with Concept Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Concept [1. Are you aware of the concept of green marketing?]	-0.123	0.065	Insignificant
Concept [2. Are you aware that green marketing products are presumed to be environmentally safe?]	-0.028	0.674	Insignificant
Concept [3. Are you aware that green marketing raise awareness on important environmental or social issues?]	-0.182	0.006	Significant
Concept [4. Are you aware that green marketing undergoes product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising?]	-0.049	0.463	Insignificant
Concept [5. Are you aware that green marketing adhering to sustainability principles while achieving maximum profit potential?]	-0.032	0.632	Insignificant
Concept [6. Are you aware that green marketing helps in waste reduction?]	-0.149	0.025	Significant
Concept [7. Are you aware that green marketing brings a competitive advantage to your business?]	-0.070	0.291	Insignificant
Concept [8. Are you aware that green marketing creates a wider choice of marketing points that can promote and discuss with the customers, which go beyond traditional strategies such as having the lowest price, durability and style?]	-0.089	0.181	Insignificant
Concept [9. Are you aware that green marketing can be more expensive, but it can also be profitable due to the increasing demand?]	-0.143	0.052	Insignificant
Concept [10. Green marketing describes a business' efforts to advertise the environmental sustainability of their business practices?]	-0.221	0.051	Insignificant

Table 9 reveals the correlation of the length of operations with concept awareness of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. Generally, it implies that length of operation and concept awareness are insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of -0.028. It pertains that the length of operations of businesses does not have a significant relationship with the concept of green marketing. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with length of operations and level of awareness towards green marketing concepts.

Table 10. Correlation of Length of Operations with Strategy Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Strategies [1. Are you aware of green product designing where products are designed in environment friendly way?]	-0.218	0.061	Insignificant
Strategies [2. Are you aware of green positioning where core component of its corporate practices, an organization should specifically support its sustainable output and that of its goods and services.?)	-0.210	0.053	Insignificant
Strategies [3. Are you aware of green pricing where a business should illustrate how a green product or service will help to conserve key resources for customers and actively participate in sustainability?]	-0.113	0.089	Insignificant
Strategies [4. Are you aware of green logistics where includes all activities forward and reverse flows between the point of production and the point of consumption of goods, information and services?]	-0.114	0.088	Insignificant
Strategies [5. Are you aware of green waste disposal where unsustainable disposal practices can be hazardous to both the environment and human health?]	-0.042	0.530	Insignificant

Table 10 presents the correlation of the length of operations with strategy awareness of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It pertains that length of operation and strategy awareness is insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of -0.042. It shows that the length of operation of micro and small businesses has no significant relationship with the awareness of green marketing strategy. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with length of operations and level of awareness towards green marketing strategies.

Table 11. Correlation of Business Organization with Concept Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Concept [1. Are you aware of the concept of green marketing?]	0.356	0.119	Insignificant
Concept [2. Are you aware that green marketing products are presumed to be environmentally safe?]	0.113	0.089	Insignificant
Concept [3. Are you aware that green marketing raise awareness on important environmental or social issues?]	0.051	0.440	Insignificant
Concept [4. Are you aware that green marketing undergoes product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising?]	0.128	0.054	Insignificant
Concept [5. Are you aware that green marketing adhering to sustainability principles while achieving maximum profit potential?]	0.214	0.061	Insignificant

Concept [6. Are you aware that green marketing helps in waste reduction?]	0.002	0.975	Insignificant
Concept [7. Are you aware that green marketing brings a competitive advantage to your business?]	0.046	0.487	Insignificant
Concept [8. Are you aware that green marketing creates a wider choice of marketing points that can promote and discuss with the customers, which go beyond traditional strategies such as having the lowest price, durability and style?]	0.123	0.064	Insignificant
Concept [9. Are you aware that green marketing can be more expensive, but it can also be profitable due to the increasing demand?]	0.163	0.054	Significant
Concept [10. Green marketing describes a business' efforts to advertise the environmental sustainability of their business practices?]	0.150	0.063	Insignificant

Table 11 depicts the correlation of the business organization with concept awareness of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It shows that the business organization and concept awareness is insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of -0.046. It pertains that the business organization doesn't have a significant relationship with the awareness of the green marketing concept among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with type of business organization and level of awareness towards green marketing concepts.

Table 12. Correlation of Business Organization with Strategy Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Strategies [1. Are you aware of green product designing where products are designed in environment friendly way?]	0.039	0.562	Insignificant
Strategies [2. Are you aware of green positioning where core component of its corporate practices, an organization should specifically support its sustainable output and that of its goods and services.?)	0.050	0.455	Insignificant
Strategies [3. Are you aware of green pricing where a business should illustrate how a green product or service will help to conserve key resources for customers and actively participate in sustainability?]	0.117	0.080	Insignificant
Strategies [4. Are you aware of green logistics where includes all activities forward and reverse flows between the point of production and the point of consumption of goods, information and services?]	0.080	0.229	Insignificant
Strategies [5. Are you aware of green waste disposal where unsustainable disposal practices can be hazardous to both the environment and human health?]	0.039	0.561	Insignificant

Table 12 presents the correlation of the business organization with strategy awareness of micro and small enterprises in Cavite in green marketing. It implies that the business organization and strategy awareness is insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of 0.039. It reveals that the business organization doesn't have a significant relationship with the awareness of green marketing strategy among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with type of business organization and level of awareness towards green marketing strategies,

Table 13. Correlation of Number of Staff with Concept Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Significance
Concept [1. Are you aware of the concept of green marketing?]	0.162	0.515	Insignificant

Concept [2. Are you aware that green marketing products are presumed to be environmentally safe?]	0.122	0.068	Insignificant
Concept [3. Are you aware that green marketing raise awareness on important environmental or social issues?]	0.032	0.637	Insignificant
Concept [4. Are you aware that green marketing undergoes product modification, changes to the production process, packaging changes, as well as modifying advertising?]	0.064	0.339	Insignificant
Concept [5. Are you aware that green marketing adhering to sustainability principles while achieving maximum profit potential?]	0.207	0.052	Insignificant
Concept [6. Are you aware that green marketing helps in waste reduction?]	0.108	0.105	Insignificant
Concept [7. Are you aware that green marketing brings a competitive advantage to your business?]	0.114	0.088	Insignificant
Concept [8. Are you aware that green marketing creates a wider choice of marketing points that can promote and discuss with the customers, which go beyond traditional strategies such as having the lowest price, durability and style?]	0.099	0.137	Insignificant
Concept [9. Are you aware that green marketing can be more expensive, but it can also be profitable due to the increasing demand?]	0.228	0.051	Insignificant
Concept [10. Green marketing describes a business' efforts to advertise the environmental sustainability of their business practices?]	0.188	0.064	Insignificant

Table 13 depicts the correlation of the number of staff with concept awareness on green marketing of micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It implies that the number of staff and concept awareness are insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of 0.032. It reveals that the number of staff doesn't have a significant relationship with the concept awareness of green marketing among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with type of number of staff and level of awareness towards green marketing concepts.

Table 14. Correlation of Number of Staff with Strategy Awareness

Category	Correlation Coefficient	p- value	Significance
Strategies [1. Are you aware of green product designing where products are designed in environment friendly way?]	0.006	0.929	Insignificant
Strategies [2. Are you aware of green positioning where core component of its corporate practices, an organization should specifically support its sustainable output and that of its goods and services.?)	0.105	0.114	Insignificant
Strategies [3. Are you aware of green pricing where a business should illustrate how a green product or service will help to conserve key resources for customers and actively participate in sustainability?]	0.051	0.446	Insignificant
Strategies [4. Are you aware of green logistics where includes all activities forward and reverse flows between the point of production and the point of consumption of goods, information and services?]	0.100	0.131	Insignificant
Strategies [5. Are you aware of green waste disposal where unsustainable disposal practices can be hazardous to both the environment and human health?]	0.134	0.044	Insignificant

Table 14 presents the correlation of the number of staff with strategy awareness on green marketing among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. It shows that the number of staff and strategy awareness are insignificant that has a correlation coefficient of 0.006. It reveals that the number of staff doesn't have a significant relationship with the strategy awareness of green marketing among micro and small enterprises in Cavite. With the given insignificance, the researchers **accepted** the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship with type of number of staff and level of awareness towards green marketing strategies.

Table 15. Challenges of Participants (Multiple Responses)

Challenges	Frequency	Percentage
1st Costly	200	37.81
2nd Lack of Knowledge	120	22.68
3rd Lack of Skill	115	21.74
4th Personal Reasons/Not Interested	94	17.77
Total	529	100.00

Table 15 presents the identified challenges in this study. The entrepreneurs have perceived that engaging in green marketing is very costly and can mean a decrease in the profit of their respective enterprise. Lack of knowledge ranked the 2nd, they are pertaining to the concrete elements and strategies of green marketing which they do not have a foundation which impedes them to participate. Lack of skill and personal reasons follows.

CONCLUSION

Based on the prevailing data sets, discussions and analysis, the researchers conclude the following:

1. Micro and small enterprises understudy were start-up to young enterprises, mostly on sole proprietorship organization type and have small number of staffs.
2. Micro and small enterprises were moderately aware with regard to concept concerning green marketing. Considerably, microenterprises were somehow aware as to green marketing strategies that can be employed in their businesses. Finally, the micro and small enterprises under study were not engaged in green marketing strategies.
3. Generally, there are no significant relationship between the participants' profile with their awareness level towards concepts and strategies as well as their engagement level as regard to green marketing practices as purported by the acceptance of null hypotheses; and
4. The challenges identified among the microenterprises were: the engagement or participation in green marketing is costly, they have lack of knowledge and skill and they are not interested due to personal reasons.

RECOMENDATION

Given the data, analysis and findings of this baseline study, the researchers formulate the following policy interventions and study recommendations:

1. Promotion of Green Marketing Practices and Strategies through Information Dissemination and Capability Trainings. The local government through coordination with the Department of Trade and Industries may collaborate to conceptualize, strategize and execute the above mentioned recommendation in order to increase the awareness level of micro and small enterprises towards green marketing concepts and strategies.
2. Provision of incentives, financial augmenting activities and avenues to increase the engagement level of small and microenterprises towards green marketing. The Department of Trade and Industries may craft program under their MSMEs sustainability and advocacy program to encourage the participation of the enterprises towards green marketing.
3. Exploration of other variables that can further showcase deeper understanding of enterprise and the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that may affect operations, profitability and business' behavior towards adoption or engagement of green marketing.

Acknowledgement

The authors express the greatest appreciation to the support given by the CvSU-CCAT administration, Research and Extension Unit, and the Department of Management Studies. All of these are lifted to our Almighty Lord's name.

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